

The Place of African Sacred Institutions in Enhancing Peace and Unity of a Nation

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Abstract

The crime rate in the nation, ranging from killing of people, destruction of houses and properties, kidnapping of people, economic sabotage by some individuals, from various ethnic groups and regions in Nigeria and the mind-set of some persons in the polity of the nation are indeed menace to peace and unity of a nation. The perpetrators of these vices emanate from communities within the ethnic groups and perhaps settlers in the communities. Their actions and activities appear not being checked by constituted African sacred institutions whose obligations are to ensure peace and unity. Thus, it becomes the thrust of this paper to examine the place of African sacred institutions in building, and developing norms and indigenous religious beliefs in African traditional religion perspective. Also, show how the norms in African traditional religious belief, fosters peace and unity of a nation. Qualitative approach method will be adopted in evaluating expressions on sacred institutions by scholars and some selected traditional religious institutions in the nation. This will indicate that norms imbibed by people from the African traditional religious sacred institutions are vital in building the desired mind-set for peace and unity of a nation. Also, the effectiveness of the African sacred institutions enhances security of lives and properties as well cohesiveness of a nation. Thus, the paper advocates for the strengthening of the sacred institutions as primal of security and continuity of a nation.

Keywords: Security Challenges, African Sacred Institutions, Nation Building, Peace, Unity.

Introduction

In the past decades in Nigeria, crime rate was not a threat to the peace and unity of the nation. The crime rate in the nation Nigeria in contemporary time ranges from killing of people discriminately, destruction of houses and properties, kidnapping of people, economy sabotage are least amongst the crimes witnessed in the nation. The heinous crimes were perpetuated by criminals within the communities in the nation. As observed by Makama Zagasola that one of the Boko Haram terrorist leaders by name Bashir Bulabuduwaye resided in Banki a community in Bama Local Government Area of Borno State in Nigeria¹. This terrorist leader is alleged to have conducted the killing of all abducted persons condemned by the Boko Haram². The activities of the Boko Haram had devastated the economy and peace of the North-East Nigeria, and by extension to some states in the North-Western region of Nigeria. Alabelewe Abdulgafar in his remark, expressed his dismay on how bandits took firm charge of some communities and villages in Chikon Local Government Area of Kaduna State³. He was specific on Birnin-Gwari villages where bandits were fully in charge of the communities by imposing taxes on the villagers before they could access their farms, recruiting youths of the communities into terrorism, forcibly marrying villagers' daughters and turning the farmers and villagers into slavery.⁴

The worrisome state of these communities are clear indications on how in-effective and in-efficient the African sacred institutions in the aforementioned communities and other communities in Nigeria where crimes and other vices occur frequently. It is expected that these institutions: Chieftaincy Council / Kingship, Votaries, age grade, priest / priestess of deities and divinities whose voices and directives enforces and enhances unity and peaceful co-existence to live up to expectation. But what have been noticed is the weakness of these institutions in enhancing peace and unity in communities. More worrisome is the inability of those in charge of the traditional sacred institutions to educate their subjects properly on indigenous values of peace and unity that are fabrics of building a community/nation and ensure its cohesiveness. In the words of Oladesu on the in-effectiveness of the

sacred institution, the youths become gullible and fickle-minded on influences from exotic cultures and lacked the skills to make informed choices on attainment of peace and productivity.⁵

Thus, the thrust of this paper will focus on exploring the obligations of African sacred institutions in communities/ethnic groups in the nation Nigeria, and recommend how the institutions should build and develop norms and indigenous religious values that fosters peace and unity. It is also to determine how the indigenous religious beliefs and values from the African sacred institutions can educate, re-educate and re-orientate people in various communities toward effective mind-set for peaceful and security consciousness towards cohesiveness of the nation. The theoretical analyses on sacred institution by Veikko Anttonen is adopted in this study to aid in comprehending the gamut in African sacred institutions; its roles in building the desired mind-set towards peace, unity and nation building. Again, the sacred theory brings to fore the indigenous religious values of the people and how they imbibe the virtuous in the traditional values to enhance cohesiveness of the nation.

The study showcases the vital role African sacred institutions offers in orientating and re-orientating people in the community towards peace and unity. Also, the study demonstrates how effective the African sacred institution enhances security of lives and property and peaceful co-existence across the various ethnic groups in Nigeria, as well, strengthening the sacred institution which is primal of security and continuity of a nation. Thus, the theoretical framework on sacred institution, challenges towards the peace and unity of a nation and the place of African sacred institutions towards peace and unity of the nation forms the bedrock on the research paper.

Theoretical Framework on Sacred Institutions

The term “sacred” as expressed by Veikko Anttonen needs its own peculiar understanding according to the particular system of beliefs where it is used.⁶ In other words, sacred in religious groups: Christianity, Islamic and African Traditional religion is been understood for what the adherents of these religious bodies terms as sacred. Thus, the concept sacred has its common-sense aspect which is readily observable to anyone within the religious bodies or who may bother to give the concept a second thought.⁷ Mircea Eliade held sacred to be not only the hallmarks of religion but its very essence.⁸ He assert that no cultural practice/institute is deemed sacred by the adherents if there is nothing that suggest sacred in the cultural systems of beliefs and practices of a particular religion. The theory suggests that cultural system or institute and its practices gives the title to religion when there are certain things or acts that are deemed sacred by the adherents of such religious bodies. Thus, sacred is comprehended in this theory, as “dynamic force that manifest itself in feelings of religious awe, in explicable sentiments or horror and dread, on the one hand, of overwhelming ecstasy and fascination on the other.”⁹

Reacting to Mircea Eliade and Veikko Anttonen paradigm on sacred, Comstock Richard speaks on behaviour as primal in conceptualizing sacred. He averred that “there is no entity called an emotion which can be examined when separated from the actor, his act, his symbolic vehicles.¹⁰ Behaviour is seen as a category that includes all kinds of activities in an institution or religious organizations that determine the concept of sacred. The shift from comprehending sacred as a feeling state of the subjective mind expressed to a distinctive kind of behaviour, determined by rules and is open to public observation of sacredness in an institution.¹¹ The success of this theory fostered the theoretical construct on sacred void of the supernatural or transcendent referent. For humans have the capacity to behave in certain carefully prescribed ways in respect to their environment without reverencing transcendental powers.

A departure from behaviour as a determinant in conceptualizing, sacred are the views expressed by Durkheim Emil and Mauss Marcel. They assert sacred as “a category of values according to which any institution, social group, religious group, ethnic or national groups creates its cognitive boundaries and categorizes itself as distinct from others.”¹² This theory advocates that what may be term as sacred is a collective decision or responsibility by those in that institution to make things sacred with regard to the symbolic representation of values. Members reaffirm and redefine these values in ritual practice in order to enhance their sense of integration as a community or institution.¹³

For Lawson Thomas, sacralization of things, objects and specific forms of behaviour are best understood as symbolic representations in which corporeality and territoriality functions as constraining structures of knowledge.¹⁴ To act in a sacred way by any institution or culturally prescribed manner will depend on the capacity of those involved to make adequate judgments about the well-formed and relationships of cultural practices as well as the capacity to understand these behaviours as part of larger aggregate of practice. Further expressions by Lawson Thomas on sacred states that “the idea of sacred is based on precariousness of the cultural categories guiding human thinking and behaviour.”¹⁵ This theory summarizes sacred as perceived in the universe in its dynamic aspects. Sacred boundaries are inexplicable due to the fact that for any particular approach of defining or conceptualizing sacred are embedded in the institution consensus which it protects.¹⁶

These theoretical expressions are views of scholars that are non-religious. Their remarks impede the conceptualization on African sacred institutions impacts in enhancing peace, unity and nation building. This is Vivid in Talgat Seisembay and Selt Kastkabassov views that there are “power that are hostile to sacred.”¹⁷ These powers are the habit, mockery that some persons displayed towards sacred instructions that priests/priestesses of deities / divinities, votaries or traditional governing councils’ directive in order to aid peaceful co-existence in the communities. Those of other religious faith in the communities make mockery of the instructions and speak ill of these orders.

In some cases, some persons in the community evoke the law in exercising their fundamental human rights against the African traditional religious believe on the concept of sacrilege. It becomes awkward for the African sacred institutions to enforce the concept of sacred in ensuring harmonious relationship in the communities. Further challenges in the non-religious expressions on sacred is what J. R. Farasteros stated. He averred “Multiple cultures in indigenous religious beliefs from various ethnic groups existed and runs parallel to each other.”¹⁸ People from these various ethnic groups lives among other ethnic groups with their cultures and religious values well imbibed on sacredness. Prioritizing concept of sacredness above these persons from the host communities that they reside becomes an effort that seems to be in futility in ensuring peace, unity and nation building process.

In religious perspective on sacred which is distinct from the expressions made earlier by scholars, sacred is been used as an attribute of situations and circumstances which have some reference to the culture-specific conception of the category of God. In other word, sacred is seen as supreme principles of life such as love, freedom, equality or justice. It implies that sacrality is employed as a category-boundary to set things with non-negotiable values apart from things whose value is based on continuous transactions. The value on life, love freedom etc. are paramount in enhancing peaceful co-existence towards nation building. This all human acknowledges irrespective of the variant culture and religious inclination.

It is on this premise that the theory on sacredness as propagated by Lawson Thomas gives adequate understanding on the place of African sacred institutions in enhancing peace and unity of a nation. Not only will his views aid in appreciating the feelings, behaviours and cognitive attributes of sacredness in an institutional role in enhancing cohesiveness, the cultures and religious perspectives of sacred brings to fore the practices and boundaries ethnic groups/communities placed on life, relationships, etc. Also, the consensus on the appropriate behaviors, feeling on sacred ensures cohesiveness of the people in nation building. The theory on religious perspective on sacred forms the theoretical framework in explaining the place of sacred in African traditional religious beliefs and practices as a religious guide in comprehending traditional institutions in Nigeria. What the traditional institutions adopts as norms and behavioural paradigms differs from non-traditional religious sacred institutions – Christianity and Islamic institutions.

Challenges towards the Peace and Unity of a Nation

Globally, nations are witnessing some threats that have challenged the peace, unity and productivity of a nation. Some of these challenges are vivid in the crime rates, economy sabotage, climatic factors and the international interest of some assumed developed nations of the world. Nigeria as a nation, has its peculiarities

of challenges that have been threatening peace, development, economy growth and unity of the nation. Some of these challenges appears to be man-made or frailties of those manning the polity of the nation.

For instance, the insecurity that is threatening the peace and unity of the nation Nigeria is highly manageable in the various ethnic groups/geo-political zones in Nigeria. The instance of Boko-Haram insurgence in the North-East and perhaps other regions of the country speak on the in-effectiveness of the African sacred institutions and the state security agents. Makama Zagazola informs how a Boko-Harm Chief Executioner lived amongst the people in Banki Bana Local Government Area of Borno, and killed innocent citizens abducted and condemned to death. He later surrounded to one of the state security agents in a counter insurgency within the Lake Chad zone.¹⁹ A similar security challenge was also noticeable in Birnin-Gwari villages where bandits held sway the entire community, imposed taxes on the villagers, recruit youths of the communities into terrorism and other criminal activities. Kidnapping, killing and destruction of properties etc. were order of the day in the north-east region and other regions of the nation. The insecurity trends became a discuss threatening the peace and unity the nation has cherished for decades before the menace of insurgency.

Dapo Akinrefon and Luminous Jannamillee speak on how religious politics and bigotries in Nigeria pose challenge to the peace and unity of the nation. The tenth republic election of the nation Nigeria scheduled for the year 2023 exemplifies the religious politics. A ruling party featured same-same faith (Muslim-Muslim) ticket to contest with other political parties and how religious elites and organizations are threatening the unity, peace of the nation. A former parliamentarian to the National Assembly was reported saying “I do not believe in the Muslim-Muslim ticket.” The reason has been that there is diversity when it comes to same–same ticket. Therefore, sticking to one faith is not a good thing to do particularly in a troubled nation as we are in today.”²⁰ The statement not only creates a mind-set among religious faith organizations, made most Nigerians not to see the competency in the candidates to govern the nation if their party and aspirants emerges winners of the election.

Still on the wrong perceptions on religious value, a bigot, citizen of Nigeria was arrested at Egypt on his way to Saudi Arabia to perform lesser Haji with his family members. Nnochiri Ikechukwu stated that the security agent alleged that the preliminary investigation so far made on the suspect established amongst others the offences of logistics supplier, aiding and abetting acts of terrorism as well as terrorism financing in Nigeria.²¹ Further statements by the security agency assert that Mamu Majmu has used his profession as a journalist and Islamic scholar to aid both local and international terrorist groups which has orchestrated the untimely death of several security personnels and innocent citizens in the North-East of Nigeria by given information to bandits and terrorist groups that escalated various acts of terrorism in Nigeria. The two instances cited portrays the wrong perceptions of religious values by adherents of religious organizations and populace in the nation. Religion has become the threatening factor to the peace and unity of Nigeria as a result of the wrong understanding and application of religious values that fosters peace, love and unity. These challenges illustrated on wrong perceptions of religious values are better checkmated by African sacred institutions that inculcate morals that eschew blood bath and criminal activities in the community. The value for life, dignity of labour and patriotism are the inspiring cardinal values by the institutions in fostering peace and unity among Africans.

Colonial Impacts on Nigeria as a Challenge

Britain indeed colonized Nigeria and other nations of the world. Their colonial impacts on Nigeria before and after Nigeria attained independence has been a discussion on the polity, peace and unity of Nigeria. Ochereome Nnanna in his view on the state of Nigeria, averred that the packaging of Nigeria for independence by Britain, doomed the nation permanently.²² He assert that the lopsided manner in which the Britain created electoral constituencies between the north and south before the pre-independence regional and federal elections in 1958 and 1959 established a mind-set that is indeed affecting cohesiveness of the nation. The north was placed on one region. While the south was split into two regions (West and East) an act that favoured the north in Nigerian politics up till date.

Again, Ochereome Nnanna alleged that Britain in colonizing Nigeria fostered military advantage to the north in all the military formations and other security institutions in the nation. They favoured the north before the independence to have more personnel's in the military and security outfits as well ensured the locations of these institutions' headquarters and operations in the north. These were acts from Britain that made other regions to have the perception that the north is placed on a position to dominate the polity of Nigeria whether under democratic or military rule with Britain always behind the north against the South.

The acts from the Britain may have posed a wrong mind set amongst the citizens of the nation Nigeria in comprehending the religious and cultural uniqueness of the various ethnic groups which had impeded peace and oneness from the people. It behoves the various sacred institutions in African to reorient their posterities on nation building that will enhance peaceful co-existence and enrich the religious and cultural heritages. This will enable the nation to undress the British thoughts and decisions that are adversely jeopardizing peace and unity of Nigeria.

Agitations from Ethnic Groups: The loop-sided appointments made on political offices and infrastructural projects cited in some regions generates ill-feelings in the minds of other regions and minority areas that holds the notion of neglect and insensitive by the Federal Government of Nigeria. This as it was observed by Oko Steve on the remarks made by Pan Igbo's cultural group known as Ohanaze Ndi-Igbo. The group demand justice, equity, fairness in the polity of the nation. They state that "Ndigbo both at home and in the diaspora, seeks justice, equity and fairness in their perceived unfair administration of the nation."²³ The statement further states that the Igbos desire a country that provides a platform and opportunities for people to contribute their utmost best to the growth of their father land that everyone in Nigeria belongs to.

The dearth of the platform and other economic issues are assumed to be primal motive of cessation agitations vis-à-vis Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), from the South-east region, the Odua People's Congress (OPC) of the South-west region, Arewa group of Northern People's Congress (NPC) of northern region, the agitation on constituting regional security outfits to combat the menace of insecurity etc. The Niger Delta region agitation by the militants is based on years of neglect in infrastructural development of the region in spite of the enormous contribution of the region to the economy of the nation. The agitations from these various groups pose a mind-set that does not enhance nation building / development. Thus, attaining to peace and unity appears to be eluding the nation in economic, political and social integration of citizens as they interact.

Military Rule Impact: The interruption of military in the governance of Nigeria was a nightmare that have not been erased in the memory of Nigerians. The military in a move to salvage the nation by stepping into power in 1966 introduced a unitary system of governance in a federal system of governance that Nigeria as a nation operate. In the words of Rotimi Fasan, the military during the reign of the then Head of States Aguiyi Ironsi unitarilized the nation. He speaks on the structural challenge introduced by military incursion into politics that has over the years deformed and rendered useless the tradition of healthy rivalry among the country's constituent units and politicians right before independence in 1960 and entrenched by the constitution of 1963."²⁴ The nation before the incursion of the military operated a semi-autonomous region that enabled the control of the region's resources and developmental plans for the region. This act of the military has incapacitated every effort made for resource control, restructuring of the nation's constitution to reflect true federalism etc. Thus, so much agitations on the management of the nation's resources emanate from all nooks and crannies of the nation threatening stability and unity of the country.

Institutional Corruption: Institutional corruption in governance in Nigeria poses a threat to the unity and development of the nation. Babalola Aare-Afe in his remark on institutional corruption averred that "corruption is the mis-use of power or authority for private gain". Similarly, institutional corruption refers to the "mis-use of institution powers or authorities for personal or material gains for themselves and others."²⁵ The act has really affected the effectiveness and efficiency of some established institutions bestowed with the responsibilities to protect life and property, mediate on disputes and provide social amenities to the populace. The security agents' activities and the judiciary are glaring instances of institutional corruption as perceived on the frivolous judgements delivered on some personal and political mediations.

In most cases, officials of these institutions, uses their office to deepen ethnicity, tribalism, ill-feelings among the citizens of the nation in the manner they administer the wealth and infrastructural developments in the country. Their acts, suggest that the wealth, resources and opportunities are not meant for all in the mind of other ethnic groups and tribes. Thus, agitations for a new country becomes an issue that appears unsurmountable towards governance, peace and unity of the nation.

The Place of African Sacred Institutions toward Peace and Unity of a Nation

Toyin Falola and Nicole Griffin averred that sacred institution in an indigenous religious understanding serves as the agents of divine or other world source. In other words, they are institutions that mediate between the supernatural world and natural world of the Africans in human forms granted with divine right as custodian of the people religious beliefs and practices and culture. The institutions with their kings or charismatic leaders are often described as shepherds, judges, peace makers etc. Each description of the institution has its own significant affirmative meaning.²⁶

The institutions operate on ideology. Ideologies are set of values shared by a group to justify their institutional power/authority to mediate on dispute amongst members of the indigenous communities in African traditional religious context and governance is the key agent of change in historical process of an institution which influences the communal norms, values, and thought processes as well the foundation of large-scale political, social, religious systems as well the institutional/individual moral codes.²⁷ At this point, some selected obligations of the African traditional religious beliefs and practices on sacred institutions in enhancing peace and unity will be brought to fore as to deepen the subjects' consciousness to live and cherish one another. Some of these obligations include:

Arbitration: The ability of the African sacred institutions known as “Emohua Supreme Council of Traditional Rulers,” an extract of Ikwerre ethnic group in Rivers State of Nigeria is indeed a pointer to one of the roles of African sacred institutions in fostering peace and cohesiveness among people and other ethnic groups. The sacred institution – Supreme Council of Emohua Traditional Rulers also known as Ohna and Urie-in-Council was able to mediate on the dispute on Paramount Ruler Throne of Mgbueto Community in Emohua. The contest was between two family members on who should sit on the throne on the community as “His Royal Highness.” The sacred institution went deep during the arbitration after both parties have made their oral statements and questioning by demanding clarification from the contestant antecedents on the throne centuries ago. The answers given clarified the mind-boggling issues surrounding the throne and served as eye opener to posterities in the royal families and the community. Based on the findings, the Ohna and Urie-in-council pronounced their judgment that forestalled the killing of human beings and destruction of properties in the community. Peace, unity and harmonious living was restored in the community within the shortest period void of frivolous adjournments and some proceedings in the secular courts that keeps matter lingering for a long period.

Mind-set of Service Rendering: Close to the Ohna and Urie-in-Council African sacred institution is the Edo Oba's Court sacred institution. Kaplan Edouwaye, in observing the Oba's Court administration informs how services are structured in Oba's Court: The Eghaevbo n'ogbe – the Palace Chiefs, the Eghaevbo n'ore – the Town Chiefs, the Uza-man' ihiro – the Seven Hereditary nobles that ranks next to the Oba in the following order: Oliha, Edomen, Ezomo, Ero, Eholonire, Oloton and the Edaiken.²⁸ Each of the structures are assigned responsibilities secrecy and ensures effective administration of the sacred institution. The idea of secrecy and service underline social, political and religious life of the Edo ethnic group as well enables the subjects to imbibe administrative structure that enhances governance and enabling environment for human capacity and infrastructural development and dedication to service of their father land.

On the younger generation development structure, the Oba's Court grouped their society into three tier age-grade associations: the elders (edion) comprise of male above forty or fifty years of age; adult male (eghele) from the ages of twenty-five to thirty years and the youths (Irogbae) from about sixteen years of age. The age-grade proves useful in the moral development of the people of Edo in different ways and underlies the city life as

a basis of male and female bonding only within lineages, but in many different kinds of associations including other religious groups, businesses, social and professional association across kin lines. The structuring of the Edo Oba's Court clearly creates a mindset amongst the people that enables them to build Edo nation to be very formidable in enhancing peace, and unity beyond the ethnic group.

Collective Ruling: Away from the two indigenous communities traditional sacred institution role in fostering togetherness of the people is the aspect of collective ruling. In Toyin Falola and Griffin Nicole notions, collective ruling by the African sacred institution implies on the positive note on maintaining the welfare of the community via what may be deemed as use of oppression of people based on solely on violence and force by the institution. The approach ensures social relationship and privileges over individual interest. Political interactions in African indigenous communities' perspective are better seen and appreciated through collective lens. Individual interests are often seen and considered as a threat to the community. Thus, bond and affiliations are established towards peace and unity of the people. For the peace, unity and progress of the community supersede individual/group quest in building the community.

Implementation of Government Policy: The process of globalization and secularization have affected modern communities in the nation. However, the African sacred institutions in most cases holds the explicit ability to declare and enforce orders, and the political powers of the kingdom/ethnic group including authority over a state political, economic and military decisions. The institution also holds the power to seek alliances and resources to bolster their political power and that of the states and nation. It is obvious modern African sacred institutions live in the context of states and they have not retained their explicit political powers; the primary sources of a modern African sacred institutions influence are their religions and cultural authorities. This authority is legitimized through conventions and traditional and its influence can be as significant as power that has physical manifestations.

Conclusion

Religion, ethnicity and national integration have become an issue that needs to be examined in its entirety towards the sustenance of peace, love and integration of all the ethnic groups in Nigeria. The globalization and secularization influences on the indigenous religious beliefs and practices on the cultural heritages of the nation, threatens the cultural values that have been a tendon to the unity of Nigeria. These cultural values that are void of vices are deemed sacred and institutionalized. Thus, the sacred African institutions if strengthened are capable of enhancing the moral virtues of love, peace, productivity, governance and cohesiveness of the ethnic groups and their agitations. The agitators and all those whose acts are orchestrating disunity, unhealthy rivalry, sabotage to the economy come from indigenous communities /reside in indigenous communities in Nigeria, where African sacred institutions exist. The African sacred institutions are indeed capable of building the nations by checkmating vices and activities that are very inimical to peace, cohesiveness of the nation.

Recommendations

1. Strengthening of the traditional sacred institution for effective and efficient governance by the States and nation.
2. Inclusion of the African sacred institutions in profiling security measures for lives and properties by the government at all levels.
3. The government at all levels should engage the African sacred institutions to re-orient and re-assure the populace on good governance that will foster peace, love and unity of the nation.

Endnotes

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